

NDC ASPECTS

NDC ASPECTS - Country fiches for national level results from Tier 1 and Tier 2 countries (Deliverable 5.2)

WP5 – National Pathways

September 30th, 2024

IDDR1

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www.ndc-aspects.eu

D5.2 - Detailed country fiches

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Tier 2 Countries Australia, Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, Mexico, Norway, Vietnam

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Tier 2 countries: Iran, Turkey, Japan, Nigeria, Russia, Saudi Arabia

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NDC ASPECTS PROJECT & DELIVERABLE PROFILE	
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D5.2 - Detailed country fiches

Preface

The NDC ASPECTS project will provide inputs to the Global Stocktake under the Paris Agreement (PA) and support the potential revision of existing Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) of the PA's parties, as well as development of new NDCs for the post 2030 period. The project will focus on four sectoral systems that are highly relevant in terms of the greenhouse gas emissions they produce yet have thus far made only limited progress in decarbonization. To advance these transformations will require to understand and leverage the Eigenlogic of those systems and take into account specific transformation challenges. These sectors are transport & mobility (land-based transport and international aviation & shipping), emission intensive industries, buildings, and agriculture, forestry & land-use, including their supply by and interaction with the energy conversion sector.

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

From February 2022 on, analyses have not been conducted for Russia as a Tier 1 country, but as a Tier 2 country by E3M.

The finalization date of Deliverable 5.2 has been shifted from Month 36 to Month 41.

The project has not provided a country fiche for Indonesia, as the national partner for this country is specialized on AFOLU-related topics, and therefore could not provide economy-wide inputs for D5.2. For this country, focus was put mostly on the deep dive work, which resulted in a high-quality detailed 145-page report on "Leveraging Multi-Business Forestry Strategies & Private Sectors' Engagement" in Indonesia, which included stakeholder engagement activities. Due to this focus, this partner could not necessarily provide economy-wide recommendations relevant to design the next round of NDCs, and therefore did not produce a country fiche.

2. Dissemination and uptake

At the international level, the country fiches will be published on the NDC Aspects website.

At the national level, the country fiches will be disseminated at the country level to national policymakers, namely through MS41 (One policy dialogue held in each tier-1 country) and through other events.

3. Short Summary of results

The information and data provided in this deliverable is the result from the scenario work performed in the Tasks 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4 of Work Package 5 - National Pathways for the six Tier 1 countries (China, EU, India, Indonesia, South Africa, United States) and the Tier 2 countries.

The country fiches have the objective of gathering insights emerging from scenario development that can be relevant to design the next round of NDCs. They should provide key lessons on (1) the long-term transformations, (2) key short term actions to be taken, and (3) insights into cooperation needs to operationalize these transformations.

The targets of the country fiches are national policymakers. They are therefore short and to-the-point, only highlighting what is most important, according to expert opinions.

D5.2 - Detailed country fiches

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This document unites the country fiches from the economy-wide scenario development work which was conducted in Tasks 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4, as part of Work Package 5. The formats in which the countries are delivered have been adapted to facilitate dissemination to stakeholders. Accordingly, the delivery of the country fiches listed below for Tier 1 countries (China, EU, India, South Africa, United States) and the Tier 2 countries constitutes evidence of the accomplishment of Deliverable 5.2.

D5.2 - Detailed country fiches

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Annex 1: Country fiches for China

By Teng Fei

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Annex 2: Country fiche for the European Union

By Panagiotis Fragkos and Faidra Filipidou

D5.2 - EU Country fiche.pdf

D5.2 - Detailed country fiches

Annex 3: Data tables for India

By Saritha Sudharmma Vishwanathan

D5.2 - India Country fiche.pdf

D5.2 - Detailed country fiches

Annex 4: Country fiche for South Africa

By Bryce McCall, Harro von Blottnitz, Caitlin Bergh

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Annex 5: Country fiche for the United States

By Ryna Cui, Alicia Zhao

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Annex 6: Country fiche for Australia

By Sven Teske, Thomas Pregger

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Annex 7: Country fiche for Brazil

By Huang Ken Wei, Thomas Pregger

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Annex 8: Country fiche for Colombia

By Andreas Meurer, Ricardo Delgado

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Annex 9: Country fiche for Ecuador

By Andreas Meurer, Rafael Soria

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Annex 10: Country fiche for Iran

By Panagiotis Fragkos, Maro Baka, Giannis Tolios, Anna Flessa

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Annex 11: Data tables for Japan

By Panagiotis Fragkos, Maro Baka, Giannis Tolios, Anna Flessa

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Annex 12: Country fiche for Mexico

By Andreas Meurer, Jordi Tovilla

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Annex 13: Country fiche for Morocco

By Panagiotis Fragkos

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Annex 14: Country fiche for Nigeria

By Panagiotis Fragkos, Maro Baka, Giannis Tolios, Anna Flessa

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Annex 15: Country fiche for Norway

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Annex 16: Country fiche for Russia

By Panagiotis Fragkos, Maro Baka, Giannis Tolios, Anna Flessa

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Annex 17: Country fiche for Saudi Arabia

By Panagiotis Fragkos, Maro Baka, Giannis Tolios, Anna Flessa

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Annex 18: Country fiche for Turkey

By Panagiotis Fragkos, Maro Baka, Giannis Tolios, Anna Flessa

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Annex 19: Country fiche for Vietnam

By Sven Teske, Thomas Pregger

D5.2 - Vietnam country fiche.pdf

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